

ADVANTAGES AND PROBLEMS OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN DISTANCE LEARNING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *This thesis provides detailed information about the advantages and problems of using interactive methods in distance learning of foreign languages.*

Keywords: *education system, distance learning of foreign languages, use of interactive methods.*

It is becoming increasingly clear that significant changes are taking place in the education system of our country. It is also gratifying that, among various forms of education, distance learning is being widely used. It is clear to many that this type of education has many advantages. A number of works are being carried out to implement distance learning techniques and technologies in all higher education institutions. The development of information technologies requires a new approach to the organization of distance learning¹. The basis of modern models of distance learning is communication and network technologies. These technologies, while opening up a wide range of opportunities for information users, also pose a problem of protecting them. The lack of direct communication between the teacher and the listener in distance learning also creates some problems. For example, certain difficulties arise in organizing the process of problem-based learning. In the preparation of a listener as a qualified specialist, communication can be carried out via teleconference. However, to solve this problem, it is necessary to develop additional educational materials. Among them, it is desirable to have problem tasks of different levels, instructions that create problem situations, etc. The main goal of the educational process is to prepare highly qualified specialists who have mastered the basics of science and are qualified in all areas. Therefore, the use of modern information technology tools in the study of foreign languages in accordance with the requirements of the present day is important. In foreign language lessons, the direct use of modern teaching and technical means,

¹ Xo‘jayev N.X., Xodiyev B.Yu., Baubekova G.D., Tilabova N.T. Yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar. O‘quv qo‘llanma. – T.: Fan, 2002.B-38.

language rooms, multimedia, specially programmed topics, multilingual electronic dictionaries is appropriate.

The use of distance learning methods, press, telecommunications and Internet materials in teaching foreign languages serves as a source of information for students not only to learn foreign languages, but also to increase their intellectual level. Among the most effective approaches to teaching a foreign language, one can single out methods of teaching languages using information and communication technologies, in distance education. There are very wide opportunities for learning languages using computer technologies, especially the Internet. They are manifested in the following:

- 1) actively use the acquired knowledge and skills in oral communication in a foreign language in practice, learning to use the acquired language materials not only in one's own speech, but also in understanding the speech of an interlocutor whom one has met via the Internet;
- 2) form the flexible ability to transfer the acquired speech knowledge to changing situations of communication;
- 3) create a strong, immediate motivation and motivation for a realistic attitude towards organizing a conversation in the form of informal communication, learning to speak;
- 4) overcome psychological barriers, in particular, eliminate the fear of speaking and making mistakes in a foreign language, the barrier, as well as the feeling of internal and external shyness and embarrassment;
- 5) increase the quality of education to a high level and immediate effectiveness; Already in the second exercise of the exercises, users begin to speak in the foreign language they are learning in the speech pattern given in the main educational text; using suggestive means of text influence (including memorization), exercises are taken into account already in the first exercise;
- 6) presentation and mastery of a large number of speech, higher and grammatical units; in one presentation, 150-200 new words, 30-50 speech samples and several typical speech phenomena are introduced and mastered.

In Internet materials, there are no high requirements for vocabulary and the volume of language materials as a condition for the implementation of speaking skills. However, speaking determines the minimum necessary amount of words and language materials that the user must master in order to fully participate as a person in the communication process.

The purpose of the distance learning course, in its most general form, is determined primarily by teaching listening and speaking in the oral form of communication in the language being studied. In addition, the extension of the course allows you to pay

serious attention to written forms of communication. Written communication involves mastering such types of speech activity as reading and writing (written speech). Expanding the educational goals of the distance learning course involves activating previously acquired speech skills, forming a higher level of communicative competence, and further systematizing the grammatical knowledge of users. The effectiveness of distance learning is one of the factors that allows listeners to retain more information in their memory, expand their awareness, and achieve better results in their work.

In addition to the above advantages and conveniences, we may encounter some problems in distance learning. First of all, it is in line with the goal to choose a method that is suitable and specific to the distance learning process. Because the effectiveness and success of each educational system depends on the methods used in it. At this point, let's define the concept of a teaching method. A teaching method is a set of interconnected methods of activity of teachers and students aimed at achieving educational goals at a modern level.

Choosing an interactive teaching method in distance learning of foreign languages is an activity that is in line with the same goal. Because the interactive teaching method serves to activate the students' knowledge acquisition and develop their personal qualities by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process. The use of interactive methods helps to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. The main criteria of interactive teaching are: informal discussions, the possibility of free presentation and expression of educational material, a small number of lectures, but a large number of seminars, creating opportunities for students to show initiative, giving assignments for working in small groups, large groups, class teams, performing written work and other methods, which are of particular importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work. Taking these into account, we can say that. The interactive method leads to many positive results in the process of distance learning of foreign languages.

The use of interactive methods in distance learning of foreign languages activates student participation, motivates them to achieve maximum results. Interactivity also helps teachers to introduce more complex material into the course².

² Saidahmedov N.S. Pedagogik amaliyotda yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash namunalari. – T.: RTM, 2000.B.7-9.

Interactivity can be combined with imitation of the environment that students need to get acquainted with during the learning process. For example, if the course involves the use of a computer program, the images on the screen should correspond to the images that should be depicted when using this program. Students should be given the task of performing an action corresponding to one of the issues being studied. For more complex topics related to this issue, it is possible to model a commercial process and recommend that the student go through it. Distance learning is a form of education that involves interactivity, implemented with special tools of Internet technologies, where the interaction between the teacher and the student is carried out at a distance and computers are used to support the learning process. From the above definitions, it can be concluded that there is no single system for understanding the essence of distance learning. However, at present, distance learning in higher education institutions is presented in the form of distance learning technology, which is not supported by the legislative framework.

The main goal of using interactive methods in distance learning of foreign languages is to involve students in the active learning process, help them develop knowledge and research skills and abilities. Interactive methods are based on the active interaction of the teacher and the student, their complete understanding of each other. The main goal of introducing interactive methods into the educational process is to organize the cooperation of the teacher and the student in the lesson, regardless of the form in which the lesson is held, wherever it is held. The teacher should involve students in the problems of the lesson, activate their actions and, as a result, teach them to master the skills.

In distance learning, the interactive method is becoming the most relevant method from today's point of view. For example, I express my opinion on a certain topic. I am interested in the attitude to it, the opinion of others, in such a situation, it is interesting to exchange opinions through the network, not only from acquaintances, but also from other users, familiar or unfamiliar, through the Internet. Representatives of different nationalities can express different opinions. Then there is an opportunity to draw a general conclusion. The interactive method can also serve to make the topic being taught more understandable. The opinion is asked, and accordingly, a specific topic is selected. A simple example is also embodied in the opinions expressed on this topic we raised.

Now let's talk about the disadvantages of distance learning; The first problem is that distance learning limits communication with people. Given that distance learning can be conducted in different locations, many students find that it provides more personal attention and interaction with their tutors and peers than traditional learning. Quality distance learning programs engage students through group projects and online discussions. Teachers respond to students' questions in a timely manner and continuously assess their work, while students have more opportunities to interact with each other.

Another challenge is whether distance learning courses are accurate in assessing students' knowledge. You can use any test from a distance. There are no restrictions on this.

Another challenge is time. You don't have control over your study time. You have the opportunity to study at a specific time.

The problem in question may be related to the technology you are using. For example, a breakdown of the equipment or a low internet speed may cause you inconvenience.

When using an interactive method in the education system, the teacher encourages the student to actively participate. In some cases, the student's reticence or shyness, hesitation in expressing his opinion openly can negatively affect the quality of education. This can certainly serve to reduce the effectiveness of education. In order to avoid such situations and eliminate such situations, choosing and applying a more interactive method in distance education compared to other educational methods will help to achieve the intended goal faster and more effectively. When organizing the lesson process on an interactive basis, the student's interaction increases, and the skills of working collaboratively and creatively are formed. Skills are formed in working with the curriculum, program, textbook, standard norms, manuals, subject content. Independent reading, work, mastering the content of the educational text becomes a daily personal task. The student gets used to expressing his opinion freely, defending his opinion, being able to prove and confirm. Most importantly, didactic motives arise in the learning process. That is, the student's needs, desires, and wishes are satisfied. The student's interest in the learning process increases. This situation raises the student to a higher level in achieving educational goals.

Now, if we talk about the advantages of using interactive methods in distance learning of foreign languages, then first of all, it leads to better mastery of the content of the education. Educational contacts are established between the student - teacher - student in a timely manner. The educational material is remembered well through mutual information exchange, receipt, and processing. The student develops the skills of

communication, expression, and exchange of ideas. Each student is able to think independently, work, and observe. In interactive lessons, the student not only masters the content of the lesson, but also develops his critical and logical thinking.

Of course, the organization of interactive lessons also has its own disadvantages. These are that the learning process requires a lot of time. In interactive lessons, it is not possible to control all students as much as necessary. When studying very complex materials, students cannot fully and clearly solve the problem, and in such conditions, the role of the teacher is often low. Due to the participation of weak students in the learning process in groups, even strong students receive low scores or grades.

The conclusion is that in such circumstances, a teacher must have highly developed thinking skills, the ability to observe problems, and the ability to solve problems in a timely manner.

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